

**SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT AMONG STUDENTS WITH HEARING
IMPAIRMENT STUDYING IN INTEGRATED AND SPECIAL
SCHOOLS**

Dr. R.K.Parua

Associate Professor

School of Education, North orissa University Baripada Odisha

Dr. Sumesh Kumar

Assistant Professor

Lord Krishna College of Education, Barara Haryana

Abstract:

The purpose of this paper is to find out the proper and conducive educational setting (integrated and special school setting) for the maximum development of the potentialities of their children. The study was carried out to determine the difference in social skills among hearing impaired students studying in integrated and special schools. The sample comprised 300 hearing impaired students studying different secondary school of Haryana and Delhi. The data were collected with the help of The Matson Evaluation of Social Skills with Youngsters (MESSY). The results show there is a significant difference between students studying in integrated and special schools on social skills in general and all the dimensions.

INTRODUCTION

The children with hearing impairment require special techniques and support services in their education regardless of the school setting in which they are placed. The objectives of good educational programme for the students are the all round development i.e. physical, mental, social, emotional and language development etc. School setting plays a crucial role in fulfilling this objective for children in general and children with special

need in particular (Kumar, 2011). Hearing impaired children should be encouraged to identify their problems, realize their own worth and potentialities. Thus, integrated and special settings do have their important influence over different aspects of developmental process (Sharma, 2004). The hearing impaired are socially disadvantaged, economically deprived and are psychologically alienated too. They may not have proper stimulating educational environment to realize their inherent abilities and aptitudes. Moreover, they are born and brought up in a different social set up and their abilities may be latent and we need to nourish and develop the same. In this regard, the policy planners and the educational experts need to be well versed with the psychological principles basically with respect to cognitive and non-cognitive abilities of disabled students so as to find out the etiology of their deficits in developmental areas and chalk out remedial measures to bring them into the mainstream of the society.

The rearing of hearing impaired children is a matter of concern for educational planner and administrator. A number of investigations have been established either by the Government agencies according to the needs of such children. The institutional separation for their education and re-habitation has provided relief to a large extent. Still role of integrated and special schools in bringing up of such children has its own problems. To study the social development of hearing impaired children in integrated and special schools is almost important since school guidance is also part of educational and rehabilitation of these psychologically deprived students. But social skills of hearing impaired children in term of integrated and special schools are untouchable variables. Hence the need was felt to study and addresses the problem to “The study of social skills of hearing impaired students studying in integrated and special schools” so that efforts could be made on part of parents, teachers, educational institutions as well as other members of the society in rendering constructive guidance to the students.

The purpose of the present study is to find out the social skills development among students with hearing impairment studying in integrated and special schools.

Research Design

The present study was a descriptive survey type of research. A sample of 300 hearing impaired students studying in different schools of Haryana and Delhi. Out of 300 students, 150 students from integrated schools and 150 students from special schools. Purposive sampling technique was employed for the collection of the sample. Adapted version of The Matson Evaluation of Social Skills with Youngsters (MESSY) was used to measure the social skills among hearing impaired students. Statistical techniques like mean, SD and t-test were used for analyzing the data.

Analysis and Interpretation of the data

Table -1

Significance of Difference Between Hearing impaired Students Studying in Integrated and Special Schools on Social Skills .

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	S.D.	SED	t-ratio	Level of significance
Social Skills	Int.Schools	92	125.34	30.39	5.04	4.78	.01
	Spl. Schools	156	101.24	23.55			

Table Value= .05 =1.96 =.01=2.58

Fig-1 Mean Scores Of Hearing impaired Students Studying In Integrated and Special Schools On Social Skills .

It is revealed from the Table-1 that the mean scores of hearing impaired students studying in integrated and special schools on social skills are 125.34 and 101.24 with S.D's 30.39 and 23.55 respectively. The t-ratio came out to be 4.78 which is significant at .01 level of significance. That means there is a significant difference between hearing impaired students studying in integrated and special schools on social skills. However, the mean score of hearing impaired students studying in integrated schools is higher than the hearing impaired students studying in special schools. It implies that the students those were studying in integrated schools had better social skills as compare to the students studying in special schools.

Table -2

Significance of Difference between Hearing impaired Students Studying in Integrated And Special Schools on Different Dimensions of Social Skills

N=300

Sr. No	Dimensions	Types of school	Mean	S.D	SED	t-ratio
01	Appropriate Social Skills	Int. Schools	35.71	7.34	0.92	1.5
		Spl.Schools	34.33	6.50		
02	In Appropriate Assertiveness	Int. Schools	20.85	4.98	0.58	6.29**
		Spl.Schools	17.20	3.50		
03	Overconfident	Int. Schools	23.34	5.82	0.68	10.42**
		Spl.Schools	16.25	4.20		
04	Impulsiveness	Int. Schools	22.67	6.01	0.74	8.85**
		Spl.Schools	16.12	5.15		
05	Loneliness	Int. Schools	22.77	6.24	0.72	7.54**
		Spl.Schools	17.34	4.20		

Df= N-2= 300-2= 298

Table of 298 df at .01 level= 1.96

At .05 level= 2.58

Fig-2

Mean Scores Of Hearing impaired Students Studying In Integrated And Special Schools On Social Skills .

It is revealed from the Table 2 that the mean scores of hearing impaired students studying in integrated schools on different dimensions of social skills like In Appropriate Assertiveness (IAA), Impulsiveness (IP), Overconfident (OC), and Loneliness (LON) are 20.85, 23.34, 22.67 and 22.77 with S.D's 4.98, 5.82, 6.01 and 6.24 respectively. The Mean scores of hearing impaired students studying in special Schools on different dimensions of social skills like In Appropriate Assertiveness (IAA), Impulsiveness (IP), Overconfident (OC), Loneliness (LON) are 17.20, 16.25, 16.12 and 17.34 with S.D's 3.50, 4.20, 5.15 and 4.20 respectively. The t-ratio came out to be 6.29 10.42, 8.85 and 7.54 which is significant at .01 level of significance. That means there is a significant difference between hearing impaired students studying in integrated and special schools on social skills on above dimension. Bu the dimension like appropriate social skills (ASS), there is no significant difference between students studying in integrated and special schools, as their t-ratio indicated that 1.50. However, the mean score of hearing impaired students studying in integrated schools is higher than the hearing impaired

students studying in special schools. It implies that the students those were studying in integrated schools had better social skills as compared to hearing impaired students studying in special schools.

Discussion and Conclusion

The present study reveals that the hearing impaired students who have studied in integrated schools have better social skills than who are studied in special schools. So it is suggested to the parents of hearing impaired children that they should admit their children in integrated schools for their better development of social skills. In special schools the teacher should make an effort to develop a conducive social climate in the class so that every hearing impaired students should feel that he belongs to a group of normal population. The study also presents that the students of integrated schools are more confident than special schools. So, there must be organize programmes drama, poetry, sports etc more to enhance the social skills among hearing impaired students. The findings also show that the students of special schools feel more loneliness and impulsiveness than integrated schools. So, it is recommended to the teachers of special schools that they should understand and identify child's self esteem to encourage and generate social skills among hearing impaired students. They can also assign some projects to develop the social skills. The impulsiveness and loneliness of hearing impaired students can be decreased in special schools with good and congenial environment because there is a keen relationship between social environment and social skills.

References

- Barraga, N.C.(1980). *Summary of Research in Visual Impairment* . Presentation at the International Institute for Hearing impaired, Sun Valley , Idaho.
- Copeland, JW.(2005). *The relationship between academic achievement and social skills among elementary students*. Proquest dissertation and thesis , Publication number 3194845,<http://gateway.proquest.com>

- Diprete, Thomas A. & Jennings, Jennifer L. (2009). *Social/behavioral skills and the gender gap in early educational achievement*. Spencer: Foundation and American Educational Research Association.
- Dray, A.J., & Selman, R. L. (2011). Culture and Comprehension: A mixed method study of children's responses to a fictional story about interracial conflict. *Reading and Writing quarterly*, 27, (2), 48-74.
- Strahan, E.Y. (2002). The effect of social anxiety and social skills on academic performance. *Personality Individual Differences*, 34(2), 347-366.
- Gillis, J.M., & Callahan, E. (2011). Assessment of social behavior in children interactions in young children. *Research in autism spectrum disorder*, 5, (1), 351-360.
- Malavika, Mokashi V. (2007). Coorelates of anxiety and scholastic achievement of residential school students. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 25(5)36-41.
- Matson, J.L., Dawson, K., & Kazdin, A. (1983). Validation of methods for assessing social skills in children. *Journal of Clinical Child Psychology*, 12, 174-180.
- Matson, J.L., Heinze, A., Helsel, W.J., Kappermann, G., & Rotatori, A.F. (1986). Assessing social behaviour in the visually handicapped: The Matson Evaluation of Social Skills with Youngsters (MESSY). *Journal of Clinical Child Psychology*, 15, 78-87.
- Matson, J.L., & Ollendick, T.H. (1988). *Enhancing children's social skills: Assessment and training*. New York: Pergamon Press.
- Matson, J.L., Rotatori, A.F., & Helsel, W.J. (1983) Development of a rating scale to measure social skills in children: The Matson Evaluation of Social Skills with Youngsters (MESSY). *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 21(4) 335-340.
- Singh, S. & Thukral P. (2010). Social maturity and academic achievement of high school Students. *Canadian Journal on Scientific and Industrial Research*, 1, 6-7.

- Soleimani, N. & Sharabi, K.(2011). The comparison of social skills and academic achievement among ordinary and multiple grade students in elementary school. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 34, 347-366.
- Vallotton, C.D. & Ayoub ,C.C.(2010). Symbols build communication and thought: The role of gestures and words in the development of engagement t skill and social-emotional concepts during toddler hood. *Social Development*, 19, (3) 601-626.
- Wu, C.Y.& Lo.Y.F.(2010).Social skills training for taiwanese students at risk for emotional and behavioral disorders. *Journal of Emotional and Behavioral Disorder*, 18(3), 162-177.